

Degree of dependence on local governments of Italian metropolitan cities and provinces

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The degree of dependence on local governments represents a measure of the percentage of financial resources that a region, province or city depends on its local governments, such as municipalities, provinces or territorial bodies, compared to the total resources used to finance its activities. It expresses the share of public spending covered by local revenues, such as taxes, duties or internal transfers, compared to revenues from external sources, such as the central government or other institutions. A high degree of dependence indicates that a significant part of the economic resources necessary for the functioning of the territory comes from local governments, reflecting a greater responsibility and involvement of the latter in financial management. On the contrary, a low value could indicate a lesser centrality of local governments in economic support, with greater financial autonomy of the territories or greater recourse to external funds. The data are made available by Istat for 2021-2022 and refer to the metropolitan cities and provinces analyzed in the regional context.

The data on the degree of dependence on local governments for 2021 and 2022 show significant variations between Italian regions, reflecting different capacities and needs for economic support at the local level. Liguria stands out for its extremely high levels of dependence both in 2021 (54.0%) and 2022 (57.1%), ranking first among the regions for the degree of local dependence. This could indicate a strong centralization of local resources or a lower autonomy of municipalities. Sardinia and Sicily also show high values, but slightly decreasing compared to the previous year, with Sardinia going from 43.9% to 44.3% and Sicily from 33.6% to 31.0%. On the contrary, the Northern regions such as Emilia-Romagna, Tuscany and Lombardy record significantly lower values, with marginal variations between 2021 and 2022. Lombardy and Lazio show a slight increase, respectively from 9.9% to 12.3% and from 11.8% to 12.2%, while still maintaining a relatively limited dependency. Regions such as Abruzzo, Molise and Marche show the lowest values overall, with almost zero dependencies or in any case less than 5%, highlighting a greater capacity for financial self-sufficiency or a more decentralized local management model. Veneto records a significant decrease, going from 28.7% to 25.9%, signaling a possible improvement in the capacity for autonomous financial management at local level. In the South, Campania goes from 17.6% in 2021 to 10.3% in 2022, indicating a marked reduction in local dependence, while Puglia shows a slight increase, from 21.4% to 22.1%. Basilicata, on the other hand, shows a drastic drop in local dependence, going from 31.2% in 2021 to 10.9% in 2022, which could be attributed to a change in policies or a reorganization of the management of local resources. Umbria also records a significant decrease, going from 23.7% to 19.2%. Piedmont records a moderate decrease, going from 13.8% to 10.0%, while Calabria shows a slight increase, from 7.3% to 10.0%. These data reflect a strong heterogeneity in dependence on local administrations among Italian regions, with the North generally more autonomous and the South and the Islands more dependent. However, some regions in the South and Centre show trends towards greater autonomy in 2022, highlighting the need for targeted interventions to promote equitable distribution of resources and greater self-sufficiency at local level.

The clustering of data relating to the degree of dependence on local governments has identified two main clusters:

- Cluster 0 groups regions with a low or moderate degree of dependence on local governments, reflecting a greater capacity for financial self-sufficiency or limited use of local resources to finance public expenditure. Regions such as Piedmont, Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna and Tuscany, historically more developed, are distinguished by a diversified economy and more efficient administrative structures, which reduce the need for local support. The presence of southern regions such as Calabria, Campania and Puglia indicates a limited use of local resources, probably linked to an economic context that requires greater support from central rather than local governments. The presence of regions with heterogeneous characteristics suggests that, in addition to economic differences, local policies and administrative structure also influence the degree of dependence. This cluster represents a balance between financial autonomy and management of local resources, which varies between the North, Center and South.
- Cluster 1, composed of Liguria, Sicily and Sardinia, highlights regions with levels of dependence on local governments significantly higher than the rest of the country. Liguria stands out for the highest values, with further growth between 2021 and 2022, reaching over 57%. This could reflect greater centralization in resource management or a local administrative system strongly involved in economic support. Sicily and Sardinia, although with lower values than Liguria, maintain a significant dependence, signaling the need for local resources to finance significant expenses or to compensate for the lack of other sources of income. This cluster suggests a regional dynamic where local administrations play a central role in balancing economic needs, probably in response to economic or geographical contexts that require more incisive interventions.

The graph clearly shows the separation between the two clusters, with Liguria, Sicily and Sardinia clearly above the others in terms of dependence. This distribution highlights significant differences in local financial dynamics among Italian regions.

The data on the degree of dependence on local administrations show a clear difference between the Italian macro-areas, highlighting heterogeneous regional dynamics. The North-West records a moderate level of dependence, growing from 18.9% in 2021 to 19.6% in 2022, indicating a growing role of local administrations in the management of public resources. The North-East, on the other hand, shows a slight reduction from 20.0% to 18.1%, suggesting greater financial autonomy or less reliance on local resources. In Central Italy, dependence remains low and stable, going from 10.7% to 10.2%, reflecting a high capacity for self-financing or a less centralized economic structure. The South and the Islands show the highest dependence values, but with a reduction between 2021 and 2022. The South goes from 15.8% to 12.1%, while the Islands, which remain the most dependent area, go from 36.3% to 34.6%. These data suggest greater economic difficulty and a strong centralization of resources in the southern and insular areas, although the reduction may indicate a gradual improvement in local autonomy. Overall, the northern regions show greater stability and autonomy, while the South and the Islands remain more vulnerable, underlining the need for differentiated policies to rebalance regional disparities.

Sources: ISTAT

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